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D 5.6

Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (M12 UPDATE)

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#HYPOPPROJECT

D 5.6	Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan M12 update
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Deliverable abstract

D5.6 is the update of the Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of Work Package 5, updated after the first 12 months of project implementation. This deliverable intends to present actions to be taken in order to strengthen and empower awareness raising about HYPOP, starting from lessons learnt and practices applied to dissemination and communication of project activities. The report also identifies the expected exploitable assets and prepares a plan for the exploitation of the project results. This document also presents KPIs achieved and compares them to the ones expected in the project planning phase.

Keywords

Dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy, outreach, awareness raising, communication toolkit, target group, exploitable asset, result, impact

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Partners short names

ENVI	Environment Park Torino Spa
IMI	Institute For Methods Innovation
IME	Fundacion IMDEA Energia
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
CNH2	Centro Nacional Del Hidrogeno
RIGP	Regionalna Izba Gospodarcza Pomorza
CLUSTER TWEED	Cluster Tweed
BH2C	Balkanski Vodoroden Klaster

Abbreviations

GA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement

Executive Summary

Communication and dissemination are of paramount importance to the success and impact of project HYPOP – HYdrogen Public Opinion and accePtance.

HYPOP shall make use of the EU H2020 and Horizon Europe projects' dissemination and communication best practices and follow the 6W approach: What, Why, When, hoW, Where and to Whom to disseminate / to communicate.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide an update to the reference document for strategically and effectively disseminating knowledge and information throughout the project. The aims to provide relevant information on the implementation of the Dissemination and Communication strategy, setting the next steps in terms of what should be done to ensure effective promotion and awareness raising about the project and its outcomes in the last 12 months of activities.

In addition, this report provides a first Exploitation Plan for the use of project results.

D5.6 is also an updated guide for project partners on how to keep promoting the project and maximising the impacts of the activities that they are carrying out, with instructions on how to use the right promotional tools and dissemination channels, how to engage stakeholders through targeted messages and adequate channels.

Present deliverable follows the strategy already defined in D5.1 - First Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan. It will be further updated along the project, specifically next GANTT month M18 (D5.7).

1 Introduction

This document is a review of the first First Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan delivered at M3 (D5.1 as per GA). The present report update defines the next main Communication and Dissemination steps, following the project's progress and integrating main results coming from WP1 and WP2.

In the next chapters, objectives, KPI and main strategy are described.

1.1. Context and background

Project HYPOP - HYdrogen Public Opinion and accePtance, Grant Agreement nr 101111933 is a project supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, and co-funded by the European Union.

Project HYPOP's Overall Objective is to raise public awareness and trust towards hydrogen technologies and their systemic benefits, through:

- the preparation of guidelines and good practices that will help to define more effectively how citizens, consumers/end-users and stakeholders can be involved in the implementation of Hydrogen technologies
- the creation of a web platform, and social media, collecting communication material, mainly videos, on new hydrogen technologies, developed according to the early findings of the public engagement activities.

To reach the overall goals of the project, 2 different target groups will be targeted, engaged and involved directly in dedicated activities:

- the first target group brings together: citizens, consumers, end users and communication experts. The project will analyze the public understanding of citizens aged 15 and above in each of the Country or Region surveyed (Public Opinion Survey, commissioned by Hydrogen Europe in early 2022 and expected to be completed by spring 2023) with a deep focus on East EU areas (owing also to the involvement of local partners in Poland and Bulgaria).
- the second one includes the following stakeholders: First responders, permitting entities, certification bodies and decision makers.

Hydrogen is one of the key components of the energy decarbonization strategy of the Union. Its contribution is considered crucial within the main European Union Policies.

The development of Hydrogen technologies and their integration into the market energy can represent an important opportunity to face the challenge of climate neutrality and the energy crisis that Europe, its economy and its citizens are currently living through.

Public awareness activities are essential for increasing social acceptance and trust in hydrogen-based technologies throughout the European Union, particularly for addressing the potential lack of

knowledge or mistrust of key stakeholders directly involved in the first phases of mass deployment in Europe.

1.2. Specific objectives, expected outcomes and impacts of project HYPOP

HYPOP strives to achieve the following specific objectives:

- Understanding public perceptions and reactions to hydrogen and fuel cell technologies
- Identification of the main individual-level determinants of public understanding and acceptance of hydrogen technologies
- Enhancing involvement of citizens in the implementation of solutions contributing to the transition to hydrogen and fuel cells
- Understanding the pathways to influence public opinion by analysis of the current depiction of hydrogen technologies in broadcasts, newspapers, and social media, and from this developing a public information strategy
- Assessment of the specific role of the socio-economic and environmental impacts of hydrogen technologies
- Clear guidance on safety and certification and support to obtain permits and authorisations for installing hydrogen technologies
- Engagement on Hydrogen Technologies' implementation
- Identifying the safety approaches and the safety barriers in a range of different Countries, in order to create a map of the main requirements (certification) for installing hydrogen technologies and facilities
- Identifying the attitudes of the different countries towards social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) of the hydrogen technologies

Through its different operational activities, HYPOP aims to achieve the objectives mentioned above, whilst the transversal work of “impact maximisation”, which includes communication and dissemination, that is acting in its support: the aim being to **leverage results and bring them to an upper level, reaching the widest possible audience of relevant stakeholders and engaging them into the project activities (in line with the stakeholder engagement strategy of the project) and the exploitation of results.**

Below the main project outcomes and expected impacts:

- Outcomes:
 - Reach a deeper comprehension of the public opinion on hydrogen technologies
 - Improvement of the social awareness, trust and reduction of the social distance to the hydrogen topic
 - Improvement of the understanding of the hydrogen technologies
 - Improvement of the scientific community and stakeholders' awareness of the public opinion on hydrogen topic, limits and possible drivers into the acceptance process
- Impacts:

- Socio-cultural (increase the knowledge and acceptance)
- Environmental/Climatic (hydrogen is a valid energy carrier used to produce clean energy with environment benefits)
- Scientific (create more efficient technologies to integrate into the market)
- Political (improvement and acceptance of the energy strategy proposed to address the challenges of reaching climate neutrality and mitigating the energy crisis in Europe)
- Economic (long-term benefits in terms of infrastructure, and energy supply at small and large scale).

2 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of project results

Communication and Dissemination are essential to the success and impact of HYPOP objectives, its expected results and impacts.

Continuously sharing internal and external information is the transversal element that is being strategically and effectively carried out by partners for this first 12 months of activities, taking into consideration all communities relevant for and interested in the project.

The current document corrects and updates the progress achieved during the first year of the HYPOP project, recording the challenges encountered, and planning the next steps to be taken in order to reach planned results for communication and dissemination objectives and maximise project impacts. This deliverable further elaborates on partners' roles and responsibilities when it comes to communication and dissemination activities, and the relevant processes and procedures to follow to ensure a smooth implementation and monitoring of such activities. The second part of the deliverable describes the Exploitation Strategy of HYPOP, identifying key exploitable assets and a pathway for their use.

The proposed dissemination and communications strategy has been following a 6W approach to ensure that every dissemination opportunity is adequately exploited during and by the project. The 6W strategy aims to clearly identify:

- **Why to communicate and disseminate:** For efficient communication and dissemination activities, the first point to be identified are the objectives of the communication and dissemination;
- **To Whom to communicate and disseminate:** Different communication and dissemination objectives will have to target different audiences; these different audiences have to be defined;
- **What to communicate and disseminate:** Different audiences have different interests and needs and will need to be addressed with different key messages defined according to the expected outcomes and impacts of the project;
- **hoW to communicate and disseminate:** Different audiences (Industries, Research Centers, Accademia, SME, Citizens, etc.) have to be reached and addressed through different channels. To be efficient, communication and dissemination activities must be well-coordinated and monitored;
- **Where to communicate and disseminate:** To fully reach its objectives, the project has to communicate and disseminate to all its target audiences and all over Europe; and
- **When to communicate and disseminate:** The project communication and dissemination both must run throughout the duration of the project, with long lasting and scheduled actions, and take advantage of opportunities that may arise during the project.

3 HYPOP Communication and Dissemination Strategy: Update

3.1 Project vision and objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy

HYPOP Communication activities have been dedicated to inform about the project’s vision, objectives, strategic relevance and key elements, while the Dissemination tasks have been preparing the ground to share the project’s results, among hydrogen key actors and others stakeholders groups, since the first deliverables will be submitted at the end of this first reporting period.

HYPOP communication and dissemination plan has been committed to maximise project visibility and objectives, and engaging relevant stakeholders to support the use of project results, while making sectorial and technical aspects of the use of hydrogen accessible to a large sector of civil society.

The present update of the Plan integrates the results of WP1, WP2 and the results of communication and dissemination efforts. The Strategy will implement the following updates to ensure a better reach of its target audience:

- Use of videos (both short and long form) to quickly raise awareness of HYPOP goals and to address hydrogen misconceptions;
- Craft messages and consider results from review of public perception literature on hydrogen and fuel cell technologies;
- Use of hashtags identified in WP1 as most common on different social media platforms to discuss challenges and opportunities of hydrogen;
- Address the most relevant doubts, concerns, and misconceptions about hydrogen as identified in WP1;
- Support the development of an international hydrogen community and stakeholders network of technicians and experts dedicated to hydrogen projects and technologies economy deployment (Target Group 2, see chapter 3.2). Promotion of the “Join Communication” website section
- Synergies with H2 projects and demo projects/initiatives with installation in public spaces met in this first project’s years. Workshops/events/website/communication campaigns will be considered as useful actions for this activity;
- HYPOP website implemented with initiatives, news and other informative contents on hydrogen technologies to create a media platform with communication material;
- Communication kit implementation, e.g. videos (at least 1 official project video), infographics (3-4 infographics ongoing) and posters;
- Other actions to boost among the Consortium: press releases, articles, events participation etc.

Collaborations with experts and other hydrogen projects, at local and European level, will be built to implement the awareness campaigns. Indeed, practical and winning experiences of hydrogen projects identified during WP1 activity (Task1.1 on Regional Hydrogen Implementation Analysis) will be used to increase the hydrogen trust in combination with the WP1 communication suggestions on hydrogen awareness and perceptions’ key determinants factors.

Thanks to the stakeholders' community built within the WP2, the Advisory Board and demo projects collaborations, the HYPOP C&D campaigns will gain more audience.

Moreover, the HYPOP website will serve as media platform to support the stakeholders' engagement, promote hydrogen initiatives and projects, other than communication and dissemination of HYPOP's activities. As first action, two specific sections on AB members and hydrogen projects reached during project's meetings and activities, will be created. The "Join Community" section on the website will be also a useful channel to directly engage the stakeholders (<https://www.hypop-project.eu/join-our-community/>) and to boost the creation of European hydrogen community around the project.

In the next 6 months, WP3&WP4 activities will enter into force with the stakeholders' and citizens' engagement activities. The Communication team will support the engagement activities and promotion of the workshops. APRE, as communication leader, will also give its support to the HYPOP's project initiatives and dissemination events. Potential opportunities of dissemination have been identified for the coming months:

- Sustainable Places Conference, Luxemburg, 23-25 September 2024 – HYPOP Dissemination Workshop application (<https://www.sustainableplaces.eu/>);
- Hydrogen Week 2024, Brussels, 18-22 November 2024 – HYPOP stand and networking (<https://euhydrogenweek.eu/>).

All partners will work together to engage their contacts' network into the HYPOP community in synergy with the communication leader APRE, as explained in chapter 3.4.

Specific C&D actions identified for the next 6 project's months have been described in the next chapters with forecast to further update the current Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan at M18 (D5.7) based on the last results in that stage of the project.

3.2 Target Groups, Stakeholders, Audience, and Key Message

During the first months of the project, the partners have developed a map of Target Groups, which is composed of Citizens and Stakeholders who could be involved in project's engagement activities or could be interested in project's results.

The key messages highlighted during the first months of the project have been developed through the implementation of different formats on social media. In particular, to answer the questions identified in D5.1, 6 original formats were developed and implemented throughout HYPOP's social media channels. The formats are: Glossary, Partner presentations, Hydrogen news, Hydrogen events, Hydrogen projects and opportunities for funding. More details about these activities are explained in D5.3 – Communication and Dissemination Activities Report with some examples here reported:

HYPOPproject @HypoProject · 9 apr

🌱 #Decarbonization is the process of lowering the amount of greenhouse gas emissions (#GHGs) produced by burning fossil fuels.
 🌊 How do you think #GreenHydrogen can help in reaching this goal for a clean energy transition?
 @CleanHydrogenEU @IRENA @EU_Commission

Our key world
 Decarbonization by 2050 in an EU Commission goal, but what does it mean?
 Decarbonization

HYPOPproject @HypoProject · 17 apr

⚡ Are you ready to #rock?

🎸 Legendary band @Metallica has announced that they will be using #electric and #hydrogen powered @IVECO #trucks and shuttles for their upcoming European tour.
 📖 Source: thedrive.com/news/metallica...
 #cleanhydrogen #sustainability #environment #concerts

LATEST NEWS
 Metallica to use hydrogen trucks in their European tour.

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🎉 #Opportunity !
 @IMDEA, Energia Spring School
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 📍 : Rey Juan Carlos University, Madrid
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📅 Save the Date!
 @CleanHydrogenEU and the @EUCommission are organizing the Hydrogen Valley Days 2024, an event in which their work with 15 #HydrogenValleys across Europe is further elaborated.
 ** More info coming soon, stay tuned!

SAVE THE DATE
 HYDROGEN VALLEY DAYS 2024 ARE COMING!
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37 post

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Figure 1 Examples of awareness and communication campaigns formats on HYPOP Social Media channels

During the first 12 months of the HYPOP Project all Partners have contributed in the development of the dedicated Communication and Dissemination Plan and Strategy, in order to be in full compliance with the target results scheduled in the GA document.

HYPOP'S TARGET GROUPS

HYPOP's Communication and Dissemination strategy has identified the following target groups: citizens, consumers, end users and communication experts (Group 1), and first responders, permitting entities, certification bodies and decision makers (Group 2).

In the first year of implementation activities, HYPOP has been mainly addressing the first Group, through the use of social media. The reason is that the first Group is the ideal audience for the general knowledge formats that have been developed, while the second Group needs more sectorial and tailored communication materials, that will be based on the deliverables that have been developed during Year 1 of the project (WP2). However, C&D activities have been planned to be delivered all along the project and to be addressed to both identified HYPOP Target Groups. The engagement activities expected in WP3&WP4 will be useful to reach all targeted project's stakeholders. New formats for raising awareness are also under planning in synergy between APRE and IMI by using their own communication and social awareness knowledge.

CITIZEN AND STAKEHOLDERS

HYPOP's Consortium has been basing its engagement strategy (for WP3 and WP4) tailoring activities for specific Citizen and Stakeholder categories. Such activities and tools are explained in the table below.

Citizen and Stakeholder categories	Key engagement	HYPOP Hub - Web Platform	Social Media	Expert Forum	Planned Events	Publication Repository	Workshops (co creation) Webinars	EU Technology pathway	Video/Infographics	Other Communication
Citizens with civil society organisations (CSOS)	Acceptance of citizens is needed for a technology uptake. CSOS will reinforce representativeness of their sectors/thematic focus for the benefit their members	X	X		X		X		X	
Experts from research/academia	HYPOP will increase the hydrogen technologies									

	visibility through promotion in experts' webinars, workshop, conference, podcasts, etc., and to increase knowledge-sharing with and between these stakeholders	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Businesses (industry, large companies, SMEs), clusters and business associations	These stakeholders will give first-end information on hydrogen technologies as they are early adopters/up-takers of new emerging technologies	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
EU, national and regional policy bodies, governmental institutions, innovation agencies	Public authorities and specifically decision makers of hydrogen technologies will be continuously targeted to be informed and familiarized with the concepts of enabling technologies	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X
Other initiatives and projects	These stakeholders contribute to community building through cross-pollination and fertilization in order to increase synergies and networks	X	X			X			X	X

Table 1 - Citizen and Stakeholders involved

We are resharing the above table in this update of the D5.1 plan, because the citizen and stakeholders involvement tools and activities of reporting period M1-M12 foreseen in this table are being complied by the Consortium.

3.3 Dissemination channels including Communication Tools

The HYPOP project has been maintaining an active online presence to lay the base of its specific identity, to communicate and disseminate relevant information and news about the project, thanks to the following channels, tools and activities:

- the HYPOP website (online from M4);
- HYPOP social media channels: LinkedIn, X (formerly known as Twitter), YouTube, Instagram;
- project news and communications published on the website and social media channels;
- project public presentation with a generic overview of HYPOP to be used in events;
- project flyer giving an overview of the project objectives, main activities and expected results;
- project roll-ups/posters/banner;
- engagement with initiatives and networks in the field of hydrogen, both at the European and international levels;
- participation in major external events and conferences of interest;
- information and knowledge exchange with and through other relevant initiatives for the exploitation of synergies.

For details on Communication HYPOP toolkit and channels refers to D5.1 – First Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan and D5.2 – Visual Identity Handbook.

More activities are foreseen for the second part of project implementation (M12-M24), specifically related to dissemination of project results through workshops, conferences, videos, infographics, and awareness raising campaigns. Potential campaigns and activities planned:

- Consortium presentation campaigns by using post cards, interview videos;
- H2 projects and demo projects, sharing of experiences from these projects by partners, involved citizens;
- H2 technologies and devices explained by experts;
- Promotion of existing educational/awareness projects;
- Infographics reporting WP1, WP2 results for this Year 1;
- Videos on HYPOP's partners, H2 technologies explanation or dissemination of existing awareness activities from other initiatives. Sharing of positive experience by citizens using H2 technologies (e.g. hydrogen buses for public transport).

3.3.1 Project branding and toolkit

The complete visual identity, declined in the HYPOP toolkit, has been developed and provided by APRE to all Partners in the project Sharepoint. All the materials that compose the project's brand identity have been consistently used, both online and in print version, to ensure the implementation of a coherent and recognisable brand.

3.3.2 Acknowledgement of funding and disclaimer

As beneficiary of support by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership, the HYPOP project has been constantly using the institution's logo, together with the EU emblem, in all its communications and dissemination materials, both internally and externally. Both logos, together with the identified disclaimer about funding, are also applied to every output of the project.

3.4 Planning of the communication and dissemination activities

To ensure the dissemination strategy stays up to date, an internal planning, coordination and monitoring process has been set up and implemented. In addition, all partners are reporting on their activities and opportunities, that can be found in D5.3 – Communication and Dissemination Activities Report.

APRE, as WP5 leader, is in charge of setting up and running the Communication and Dissemination Plan in all its tasks and subtasks, with the cooperation provided by all Partners.

Each month, APRE has been developing an editorial plan for the following month, in which all relevant news, information, and events are collected in order to be shared on the project's social accounts and website. Partners are asked to review and contribute to the Plan, to ensure that the content is updated and technically correct.

3.5 Partner's rule in communication and dissemination

APRE is the leading organization of Work Package 5, and has been overseeing all activities and tasks related to it, with the cooperation of all Partners.

APRE develops original content and supports Partners in sharing their relevant news, events, and materials developed for the project.

The work task responsibilities are distributed as follows:

APRE – Work Package leader:

Leads the management and coordination of the work package including:

- setting up of the communication and dissemination strategy
- monitoring and coordinating the dissemination and communication activities throughout Europe
- interacting with all partners for the dissemination and communication activities, and
- stimulating partners to provide dissemination input, such as news for publication on the project website, etc.
- drives the dissemination including communication activities
- provide text of relevant news and publications related to general project activities
- ensure quality control of the information provided
- creation of a visual identity and provision of templates (Logo, Word and PowerPoint)
- production of promotional material based on the contributions from partners

- set up and update of the project website
- prepare and organize the distribution of the press releases (disseminated by all partners through their channels)
- ensure the quality of the dissemination towards experts, and
- manage the HYPOP expert talks webinars, dialogue and contact with “external partner” (ex. Fuel Cells & Hydrogen Observatory).

All Project Partners:

All Partners (using the Editorial Plan developed by APRE):

- use the project’s visual identity for any dissemination on the project
- provide contributions/material for public use on the project website and communication material upon request (e.g., use case descriptions, logos, etc.)
- provide news and/or communications on important activities and achievements related to HYPOP
- inform APRE about possible participation in conferences, workshops, etc. related to HYPOP
- provide short texts about participation in events for the news section of the project website (accompanied by related links and pictures whenever available)
- disseminate HYPOP information, materials and deliverables through their channels and networks, notably in the format of newsletters, press communications, social media posts, etc
- regularly inform APRE about which communication channels and networks were used, and
- provide the required information for the reporting for the EC (see template in Excel sheet provided by separate mail to the partners).

3.6 Communication and Dissemination monitoring

Measurable targets and performance indicators have been set for the dissemination work. Besides the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) a monitoring is being provided with all the Consortium efforts for Communication and Dissemination activities in Deliverable 5.3 – Communication and Dissemination Activities Report.

Table 2 shows C&D project’s KPI and their current status:

#	KPI	Target	Audience	Status at M12
1	HYPOP's visual identity and related promotional	<p>N. of brand identity kit released: 1</p> <p>N. of social media banners: 2</p> <p>N. of flyers: 2</p> <p>N. of roll-ups: 2</p> <p>N. of informative posters >2</p> <p>N. of flyers distributed >2000</p>	<p>Scientific experts,</p> <p>Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers,</p> <p>community at large</p>	All materials developed
2	Design infographics and develop informative videos	<p>N. of informative videos to explain hydrogen and its application translated in 5 languages (incl. English): >3</p> <p>N. of infographics to visualise project's outputs translated in 5 languages (incl. English): >5</p>	<p>Scientific experts,</p> <p>Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers,</p> <p>community at large</p>	Ongoing, videos and infographics will be developed and published in Y2
3	Website and social media accounts (LinkedIn, X, Instagram)	<p><u>Website:</u></p> <p>N. of website online (M4): 1</p> <p>N. of total visits: > 15.000</p> <p>N. of countries reached >27</p> <p><u>Social media:</u></p> <p>N. of accounts setup and active (M6): 4</p> <p>N. of posts per year (total): >50</p> <p>N. of social media campaigns: >5</p> <p><u>N. of LinkedIn//X followers:</u></p>	<p>Scientific experts,</p> <p>Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers,</p> <p>community at large</p>	<p>Website online since M4, website visits around 1.500 from 12 countries.</p> <p>Social Media accounts set up (LinkedIn, X, Facebook, Instagram), 36 posts shared on each social media account.</p> <p>Social media campaigns will be implemented in Y2.</p> <p>LinkedIn followers: 255 followers in Y1</p>

#	KPI	Target	Audience	Status at M12
		<p>Y1: n° 700</p> <p>Y2: n° 1000</p> <p><u>N. of Instagram followers:</u></p> <p>Y1: n° 1000</p> <p>Y2: n° 500</p> <p><u>YouTube viewers:</u></p> <p>Y1: n° 300</p> <p>Y2: n° 600</p> <p>N. of general local event per country participated by the local partner): >1</p> <p>N. of article/radio or tv interviews in national or regional media by local partners for each partner country: >1</p>		<p>Instagram followers: 133 followers</p> <p>YouTube followers: 5, no video in the channel yet</p> <p>Events KPI achieved, article under monitoring.</p>
4	Participation in external events and conferences and promotion through traditional media channels (*)	<p>N. of participation in events with dedicated booths: >3</p> <p>N. of speeches at events and conferences (live and online): >5</p> <p>N. of articles in newspapers, magazines or radio: >8</p>	<p>Scientific experts,</p> <p>Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large</p>	<p>Press Releases are planned in Year 2.</p> <p>Some events have been identified: the EU Hydrogen Week, November 2024; the Sustainable Places Conference, September 2024. Other events will</p>

#	KPI	Target	Audience	Status at M12
		N. of press releases (to 10.000 + contacts): >6		<p>be identified in each country and the best option selected in order to reach the target.</p> <p>Some magazines have been identified for articles production. WP1&WP2 results will be mainly reported with engagement activities planned in Year 2.</p> <p>Press releases planned for Year 2 mainly or just after results at M12.</p>
5	Joint activities with other initiatives and networks	<p>N. of joint activities (expert meetings): 1</p> <p>N. of mutual learning workshop: >1</p> <p>N. of online meetings with Fuel Cells & Hydrogen Observatory: >3</p> <p>N. of online meetings with EU Clean Hydrogen Mission: >3</p>	<p>Scientific experts,</p> <p>Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large</p>	<p>1 meeting with Fuel Cells & Hydrogen Observatory done.</p> <p>1 meeting/synergic activities planned with H2IT - Italian Hydrogen Association to support public and stakeholders engagement.</p> <p>The activities in this part of the table are specified in D5.4.</p>

#	KPI	Target	Audience	Status at M12
6	Interconnection with hydrogen demo-project	N. of joint activities, demonstration event: 4	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large	The activities in this part of the table are specified in D5.4.

Table 2 Project's KPIs for Dissemination and Communication and related activities

An update on the dissemination activities has been made during the last General Assembly meeting (20-21 of May 2024) where the KPIs and its reach have been discussed by the Consortium.

The results of Y1 activities have generally been under the expected KPIs, and a corrective strategy has been developed and will be implemented by APRE, with all Partners' cooperation.

The challenge encountered, mainly in involving followers on social media platforms, will be corrected through the development of project-specific materials, based on the deliverables produced by Partners.

Moreover, the project accounts will be populated with more visually engaging materials, like videos and infographics, that have the power to easily involve target groups that have been only minimally reached.

Finally, specific and tailored materials will be developed to engage particular target groups through the intervention of sectoral experts that can address their specific needs.

A Dissemination Tracking File has been also set up by APRE to monitor the partners communication activities along the project.

All HYPOP's Partners during the first 12 months participated to a dedicated European Hydrogen events. To see all events attendance, please consult D5.3.

4 HYPOP Exploitation Strategy

4.1 Introduction & Objectives

Clean hydrogen is an energy vector used as fuel or for energy storage with technical and environmental advantages, due to its versatility, scalability, and, for green hydrogen, low carbon emissions.

Hydrogen is one of the key components of the energy decarbonization strategy of the Union. Its contribution is considered crucial within the main European Union Policies, in particular the Clean Energy package (Renewable Energy Directive REDII, REDIII1), the Green Deal, the European Hydrogen Strategy.

The transition to hydrogen and fuel cells is a long process that involves different stakeholders: policy- and decision-makers, technology providers, adopters, users and, last but not least, citizens. Understanding how the latter perceive hydrogen, together with a knowledge of the needs and barriers of technology providers and decision-makers, are fundamental elements to ensure a successful implementation of solutions for the transition in terms of policy, technical development and social awareness.

The HYPOP Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation (M1-24) activities will be discussed in WP5.

In this preliminary exploitation plan the consortium will be identifying (sub task n° 5.1.1: *Target Groups Map*):

- WHAT are the most relevant exploitable project results
- WHO will benefit from such results
- HOW will such results made available
- WHY it's important to make such results available.

4.2 HYPOP key end-users

The identified HYPOP's key end users are grouped using the following categories.

4.2.1 Experts from research/academia

Specific Categories: Scientific Communities

Scientists and researchers, digital, industrial and social technologist, intellectuals and academic educators, and other profiles connected to the academical and scientific community, are interested in the results and impact of HYPOP Project. They have multiple interest on HYPOP topics (hydrogen for transportation, heating, energy). They can use them for networking purposes, inspiration, information, new research lines identification, new development possibilities, knowledge transfer, potential innovation projects as well as dissemination, reputation building, new areas specialisation, visibility and teaching materials.

4.2.2 Businesses (industry, large companies, SMEs), clusters and business associations

Specific Categories: Hydrogen Technology Manufacturers and Provider

Industry and large companies as well as SMEs and entrepreneurs are interested in new trends, new legislation, norms and recommendations. Looking for information to be more competitive, sustainable and integrated into society. And, specially, be aware of the new legal requirements based on social and environmental impact conditions that are expected to be requested in next years (climate neutrality, clean energy production, green carbon free solution, etc.).

4.2.3 EU, national and regional policy bodies, governmental institutions, innovation agencies

Specific Categories: Decision maker, Public Authorities, EU and local projects, Experts on hydrogen technologies and communication

European Commission and other EU-level policy stakeholders have great interest to use Hydrogen assets to provide evidence and advise for new European Public Policies aimed to develop the competitiveness of Europe by integrating societal and environmental aspects (climate change, energy crisis, etc.) into technology development.

European strategies are followed by national, regional and local governments that, usually, try to be in line European Policies and strategies.

The target of the HYPOP project is to involves the following dedicated thematic networks:

- *National level: organization coordinating and representing hydrogen actors at the national level*
- *European level: European networks of actors involved in the development of hydrogen value chain*
- *International level: initiatives which link hydrogen networks and projects at the international level*

4.2.4 Other initiatives and projects based on thematic and methodological interest

Advisors, consultants and mentors as well as social and technological innovators are key-end-users.

They provide different types of services and vision related to the promotion, research, design, prototyping and validation, activation, dynamization and evaluation of technological pathways and future scenarios.

They allow the improvement and acceptance of the new energy strategy proposed to face and reach the challenges of climate neutrality and energy crisis in Europe, together with a change of citizens' perceptions for the proposed new energy solutions using Hydrogen Technologies.

Tailored exploitation activities will be included in a European-wide campaign aimed at raising awareness about hydrogen, promoting stakeholder engagement activities and enhancing the uptake of HYPOP's results.

In particular:

- engagement of the relevant Hydrogen Technologies Players and End Users
- define a project Brand identity that is consistent and easy to recognise, perceived positively by the different Target Groups
- provide dedicated materials (news, scientific papers, videos, etc.) useful to obtain the awareness about HYPOP's aims and objectives

- provide a better information about hydrogen and its applications, especially among young citizen, minority, etc.

4.2.5 Citizens with civil society organisations (CSOS)

Specific Categories: Citizens, Clusters, Territorial Associations, Networks, Hydrogen Communities

Professional associations, interest groups, the media, foundations, NGOs, cultural entities (with different age, gender and background), among others, may be interested in both the assets generated by the HYPOP project and the social, economic and environmental impacts that the introduction of hydrogen technologies entails.

These entities, in addition to exploring the potential social and green/ecological applications of hydrogen solutions, may also be interested in learning more about them to raise potential ethical and moral dilemmas such as transparency, open access to data, carbon free approach, new social inequalities, etc.

These debates have an impact on the media, on the Internet and on the cultural industries in general.

Important to include in the HYPO Project minorities, youth and elders with limited knowledge about hydrogen and related technological applications and solutions.

In particular is necessary to increase acceptance, knowledge and trust in hydrogen as clean energy source and valid technologies to use in different applications. Will be necessary to understand the effects of the climate change, energy crisis and the possible green solutions currently offered by the Hydrogen technologies available.

A significant opportunity for CSOS to have their voice heard will be the discussion on the indicators for the Social Life Cycle Assessment related to Hydrogen Technologies.

4.3 Planning of exploitation

The exploitation planning has been set up to ensure the following four objectives:

- support the project's engagement activities by reaching out target groups and promoting the initiatives
- ensure that project's outputs (such as guidelines, best practices and toolbox) are disseminated among the identified audience
- establish links and synergies with running projects and international initiatives in the field of FCH
- exploiting project's results beyond the end of the project, ensuring they are findable and accessible in the long term.

To optimize the HYPOP's results the best exploitation plane will be analysed, discussed and definite by the Project Team during the WP5 activities, and taking into account the interests and expectations of the stakeholders involved.

4.3.1 Steps for reach HYPOP's objectives

To reach the HYPOP's objectives, the following three steps has been individuated:

- Step 1:** Analysis
- Step 2:** Engagement/consultation of the Target Groups
- Step 3:** Results

Figure 2 Steps necessary to reach the HYPOP's objectives

5 Conclusions

This deliverable has been providing an overview of the implementation of the Communication and Dissemination Plan previously explained in D5.1 – First Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (M3). Moreover, this update aims to set up corrections and adaptive measures to the aforementioned plan, with the goal of helping maximise the project impact and support the dissemination of project results. WP1 and WP2 results have been used as reference to improve the strategy and set up new activities, taking also advantages of contacts and stakeholders gained during this first project's year.

The reaching of certain KPIs needs more finetuning, that has been foreseen for the second year of the project through the use of more visually engaging materials, that can help making the content more accessible and involving for different target groups.

Next document's update according to the last HYPOP's project findings is planned at M18 with D5.7 - Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan.

6 References

General Reference:

- GRANT AGREEMENT - Project: 101111933 – HYPOP – HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2022-2, 12/05/2023
- CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT - rev. 0, 13/03/2023
- D5.1 First Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan - M3
- D5.3 - Communication and Dissemination Activities Report - M12
- D5.4 - Networking with other projects and initiatives Report - M12

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